

WEST ASIA AND THE EMERGING GEOPOLITICS OF ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE (AI)

Vrushal T. Ghoble

Associate Professor, Centre for West Asian Studies (CWAS)
School of International Studies (SIS), Jawaharlal Nehru University
Email: vrushal_jnu@yahoo.co.in

Abstract:

West Asia has experienced a structural transition. The labour force that supported the Gulf states' enormous industrial program has been the main driver of growth in the Arab Gulf. The labour force has evolved, and the region where the Gulf's demand and the requirement for a foreign labour force coincide has consistently boosted the foreign labour force. Sources estimate that the GCC alone is home to almost 30 million foreign workers. However, the expansion and advancement of West Asian nations also indicate the evolving technological landscape. The paper makes an effort to imagine how AI would develop in all fields. The essay establishes a duality for human-technology interaction and places AI into the expanding infrastructure context of West Asia. The region is now self-sufficient and technologically up to date with the rest of the globe, thanks to the developments in the area, which also fundamentally alter the rentier system. The article examines the future timeline that sheds light on how AI will affect the region in both socioeconomic and cultural dimensions. This is because the diversification process has been sparked by the Vision documents that many West Asian countries have adopted, which necessitate technological know-how. AI would be the trump card for the wealthier Gulf states, notwithstanding the region's mix of crises and realignments. The fact that Saudi Arabia granted citizenship to the robot Sophia, for example, offers a new viewpoint on the developing geopolitics of AI. As a result, there is a common image of AI invasion in the future.

Keyword: Qatar, Gulf State, AI, Geopolitics, Socioeconomic

New Geopolitics around AI Development

Since West Asia has undergone permanent change, a number of geopolitical events in the region have resulted in unrest. Because of the

shifting geopolitics, the street has grown agitated. The rentier systems of the majority of West Asian nations are moving towards a more autonomous classification, which is causing a change in the fundamental framework upon which the region was built. A sizable portion of the populace slept and depended on the money made from the sale of petrol and oil. This crucial shift occurred after 2011, when low oil prices caused oil revenues to plummet, raising doubts about the regimes' viability.

Along with this, additional events in the region signalled a geopolitical shift from old scenarios to new West Asian objectives. A notable development in the area has been the introduction of new technology, which is emerging and being adopted hands-on by the world in general and West Asia in particular. The introduction of new technologies into the worldwide market has prompted everyone to consider the future of humanity in all aspects. This new technology can express what is happening in the worldwide economy. Every invention and development around the world primarily transmits the thoughts of Western nations, which have always paved the way for the world. As a result, common convergence zones are important aspects of artificial intelligence (AI), which will bring people together. Thus, Artificial Intelligence will be an integral part of the global technology and knowledge-sharing framework in the next years.

The concept of AI is built on data collecting, data input, and training machines to follow a predefined format. It also represents a new workplace culture that emphasises problem-solving skills. It has the potential to maximise the use of various resources while also increasing delivery efficiency. Regardless of how much is spoken about the oil-rich West Asian countries that are losing revenue due to low oil prices, some are fundamentally affluent and have accumulated enormous oil wealth over many decades. This is demonstrated by their vast portfolio of Sovereign Wealth Funds (SWF). Thus, it is apparent that West Asian oil-rich countries will be among the few to adopt or are already on the route to artificial intelligence in the future years.

Once the technology is developed, man devises means to equip it with specialised decision-making power. This decision-making capability came in the form of questions such as What, How, When, and Why. This skill allows the human mind to learn the available technology. As a

result, a human being could master the skill of interacting with technology. This is where artificial intelligence could be observed. AI is now widely used in all fields of technology. The most typical examples include the usage of voice recognition in a cell phone or laptop, interactive robots, drawing future projections, and so on. The geopolitical change from a traditional perspective to a startlingly modern set of frameworks is a relatively new occurrence that has strengthened power relations among West Asian countries. Since 2022, AI has invested in several sectors, as seen in graph 1.

Graph 1: Investment in AI in various sectors globally (in Billions)

All figures are approximates.

Source: *Data collected from*, Kennedy, Alan (September 13, 2023) “Ranked: Artificial Intelligence Startups, by Country”. Accessed 09th December 2023. See, <https://www.visualcapitalist.com/sp/global-ai-investment/#:~:text=The%20United%20States%20and%20China,invested%20in%204%2C643%20companies%20cumulatively.>

The AI architecture being built is capable of asking questions and identifying potential responses. The race for new AI-powered technology also suggests that wealthy Arab countries are projecting their power. Only countries with the financial resources to invest in AI-based technologies will survive in this race. Simultaneously, AI-based technologies will succeed and become a popular medium among the people; hence, at the national level, adopting AI will yield real outcomes and aid in further legitimising and empowering administration.

West Asia and the Emerging Geopolitics of Artificial Intelligence (AI) - Ghoble

Furthermore, at the regional level, the use of such technologies has benefited the government, propelling these countries to the top of their respective regions. At the international level, power projection is also beneficial because AI-based technologies command international attention and respect, resulting in an egalitarian position in the global arena.

“The United States and China remain at the forefront of AI investment, with the former leading overall since 2013 with nearly \$250 billion invested in 4,643 companies cumulatively (Kennedy, 2023).”

Understanding the geopolitics of AI has both positive and negative ramifications. As a result, AI policy must take a variety of approaches in order to benefit humans. As AI spreads over the world, the mode of operation for an assertive future becomes more technologically advanced and sustainable.

AI in West Asia’s Emerging Architecture:

The importance of AI in West Asia and the rising architecture around it is fascinating, and it has spurred a lot of research and development (R&D) in developing human-created intelligence. It is unclear whether AI can drive West Asia in the direction it has advocated. Nevertheless, the six Gulf States are actively involved in the deployment of AI-based technology, giving their countries a futuristic image, such as countries like Saudi Arabia and the UAE. The usage of AI in the Gulf countries and throughout West Asia shows how growth and development have occurred.

“Some of the countries in the gulf like Qatar, Oman and Saudi Arabia and within the region countries like Israel are at the forefront of establishing technological networks with the help of AI with an investment of \$11 Billion (Kennedy, 2023).”

For several of these countries, AI is a component of their evolving economic strategy, also known as diversification; hence, a technical boost with AI is part and parcel of a plan described as moving away from oil and is fully incorporated in their Vision plans. AI has gained exponential stimulus in this development plan, and it has become a source of fascination and astonishment for worldwide citizens. The current circumstances and government endorsements demonstrate that

Artificial Intelligence has a well-rounded participation in all sectors of these countries; thus, AI's architecture has significantly increased the involvement and investment of public and private entities. It can be observed in both the public and new start-ups that have embraced the vision of AI and incorporated it into the national policy, which aims to build in technology that is applicable to all sectors. Globally, all nations are seeking to incorporate AI-based mechanisms into their technologies through study, data collection, and practical application in technologies being developed for the greater good; West Asia is not excluded from this race. The following graph 2 depicts AI's impact in several West Asian countries by 2030.

Graph 2:

All figures are approximates.

Source: Data collected from, Price Waterhouse Coopers (PWC), "Which regions will gain the most from AI?", Accessed 10th December 2023. See, <https://www.pwc.com/ml/en/publications/potential-impact-artificial-intelligence-middle-east.html>

The AI design also maintains connectivity and promotes the one-earth idea by making systems transparent. One of the most important prerequisites for AI growth is a network, which is not available everywhere in the world. AI development has progressed dramatically since its inception in 1940, thanks to continual innovation in the field. Many countries around the world, particularly in West Asia, are investing billions of dollars in the study, development, and use of AI-

based technology in their daily lives. The emerging AI paradigm has immense potential, which could influence other variables. In comparison to emerging and undeveloped countries, capital-rich countries are likely to undergo significant transformations in the future decade. Thus, while the phrase AI sounds fancy, it is also related to sustainable living. It is actually intended for the developed world. Nonetheless, the flow of AI-based information may eventually trickle down, benefiting everyone involved. Even if the UAE has been at the forefront of the AI revolution, other financially wealthy countries in the area, such as Riyadh, desire to be the leader and compete with Abu Dhabi in this race. Aside from the UAE, Saudi Arabia and Qatar have made significant strides and expressed a strong desire to develop and implement AI policy in their respective countries. According to reports, AI, together with oil, has the potential to be a game changer in bringing the region together and catalyzing convergence of ideas and policies. As a result, several AI businesses have received financing.

“.....it is said that the role of AI in the MENA (WANA) region’s economy will be \$320 billion by 2030 (Zartek)”.

Addiction to oil has been a prevalent expression among West Asian countries that rely heavily on oil earnings. The Gulf countries have relied heavily on oil rents.

According to Yakov Livshits, who runs startups says,

“The way governments in the Middle East (West Asia) think about AI and advanced tech in general is very bold — they want to move fast,.....(Xiao, 2023)”.

West Asian countries have struggled because they are addicted to oil and gas, yet relying on sales to balance their budgets. However, the vision writings expressly mention a revolution or movement that transcends hydrocarbons. West Asian nations, particularly those in the Gulf, have demonstrated promising signals of acceptance and non-aversion to fresh concepts and breakthroughs in artificial intelligence. West Asia, which is risen by conflict, has regularly shown signals of volatility and slowness, causing investors concerned. The economic benefits of new technology are recognised and implemented methodically in all aspects of life. Building non-oil sectors that will employ a lot of young people has been the only goal of new technology. The new AI-based architecture will

demand the population to upgrade their knowledge and skills in order to find jobs. To illustrate their dedication to adopting AI into their culture, numerous West Asian governments have released vision papers that strongly emphasise AI. They admitted that in the coming decades, AI might take over the globe. The issue of securitisation has also impeded the West Asian region. The regional actors' concerns and difficulties span from terrorism threats to energy security and food security, particularly in the context of the Ukraine crisis, to small states and their problems, among others.

“Cyberwars are a concomitant feature to physical wars. Face recognition, military drones, attempts to make various installations self-destruct have by now well-established programming procedures. Given the political tensions in the region, the UAE has invested heavily in Cybersecurity (Abadzi & ElAsad, 2021).”

Following the Arab Uprisings, the region is seeing dramatic changes in all spheres, including social dynamics. People in the region are demanding more freedom and rights, with many of these demands centred on infrastructure and necessary changes. West Asia is betting big on the post-oil scenario and wants to heavily engage AI. The oil-rich Gulf countries are pioneers in this regard. The Gulf countries, who have a lot of spare income, are investing in AI-based technology. Urbanisation is another important driver of development and diversity in West Asia's Gulf economies.

“Motivated by technological developments, these diversification initiatives will have far-reaching effects in addition to diminishing the hydrocarbon economy (Ghoble, 2023).”

Many countries are recreating their pasts in order to promote tourism and urbanisation. Heritage sites and new towns are being constructed as multibillion-dollar undertakings. Al-Ula, a historic monument in Saudi Arabia, is being renovated in stages to boost tourism. According to some sources, a new metropolis called NEOM is intended to engage the world with Saudi tourism while also engaging people with artificial intelligence.

West Asia and the Emerging Geopolitics of Artificial Intelligence (AI) - Ghoble

“In February (2023), Saudi Arabia alone announced a \$2.4 billion startup fund to help diversify the nation’s economy (Xiao, 2023).”

The majority of this fund is anticipated to be utilised for the Kingdom's AI advancement. Additionally, Sophia, a robot that represents a highly developed artificial intelligence system that can carry out a variety of duties, is located in Saudi Arabia.

“The Vision document 2030 built around a pulsating society and a striving nation. It spells out the new strategic necessities of Kingdom’s political economy of transition to post rentier process by geo-economic shift from extractive to AI lead infrastructure based growth (Pant & Ghoble, 2023).”

AI's development has been transformational, from its inception to its current state. It altered people's perceptions and experiences with technology. The examples provided demonstrate the engagement and adoption of AI in financially sound economies such as Saudi Arabia and Qatar.

West Asia and Utility of AI in West Asia:

The usage of AI in various sectors is gradually becoming the new normal in West Asia. It has become widely used in a variety of industries, including oil and gas, healthcare, government, tourism, hospitality, security, transportation, healthcare, social networks, media, and advertising. AI will also have a significant impact in the education sector. AI has been established as an obligatory lesson in the UAE's education system beginning with pupils aged four. The UAE has also launched an initiative called "One Million Arab Coders" to promote digital skills among its individuals (Dubai Future Foundation). AI-powered technology has been used by many West Asian countries. Below is a list of West Asian businesses where AI is anticipated to have the biggest impact. AI's use in the energy industry has expanded over the years. According to one report,

“... AI algorithms can predict consumption patterns using historical and real-time data, which can help utilities allocate resources more efficiently. In the same way, AI can also help optimise resource allocation. For example, during sudden periods of high demand, AI can improve the distribution of

electricity, ensuring that power is directed where it's needed most and prevent the risk of blackouts (FDM Group, 2024)."

Furthermore, AI assures this by allowing for real-time responses to changes in the energy market, as well as facilitating a collaborative collaboration between oil/gas producers and customers. AI automated systems can evaluate unstable circumstances. Another big oil corporation, ADNOC of the UAE, applied AI in the energy industry, and according to ADNOC's website, the usage of over 30 AI tools by ADNOC allowed them unlock a value of US\$500 million and even cut CO2 emissions by 1 million tonnes in 2022-23 (ADNOC, 2024). Consequently, H.E. Omar Bin Sultan Al Olama was designated the first Minister of State for Artificial Intelligence.

"UAE's AI strategy includes some of the policies like the Smart Dubai strategy that looks at the city through innovation and digital transformation; Dubai 3D Printing Strategy looks at construction, medical products and consumer products sectors; and, Dubai Autonomous Transportation Strategy that would help automation (PwC, 2018, p. 6)."

AI will also be quite beneficial in the energy industry, where applications such as digital analysis can be effective. This will aid in maximising electricity generation at a lower cost. AI's applications in the hospitality industry will also be substantial. AI-powered technology has been used to improve health care for everyone. For example, the UAE government's AI-based technical breakthroughs, having made significant investments in the field.

"The Dubai Health Authority (DHA) established the Dubai Health Innovation Centre to drive innovation in healthcare technologies, including AI solutions. In Saudi Arabia, the government's commitment to enhancing digital health initiatives is evident through a dedicated allocation of SR180 billion (US\$50.3 billion) for research and development in the healthcare sector (Mubarki, 2024)."

The use of artificial intelligence has changed the healthcare business in a way that has helped millions of people. King Faisal Specialist Hospital & Research Centre (KFSH&RC) in Saudi Arabia was the best example of how AI can help healthcare.

West Asia and the Emerging Geopolitics of Artificial Intelligence (AI) - Ghoble

“The hospital's website says that in 2023 alone, KFSH&RC performed 1,195 robotic-assisted procedures and introduced innovations like the Harmony Transcatheter Pulmonary Valve (TPV) (King Faisal Specialist Hospital & Research Centre [KFSH&RC], 2024).”

For some of the regional economic powerhouses like UAE,

“The strategy is billed as the first of its kind and is projected to achieve the UAE Centennial 2071 objectives, enhance government performance through investing in AI adoption. The UAE's AI strategy covers development and application in nine sectors: Transport, health, technology, education, environment, space, renewable energy, water, and traffic (Abadzi & ElAsad, 2021, p. 260).”

AI's use of data has changed the transport and logistics industries all over the GCC. Using AI makes it possible to make decisions based on data and find the best route. AI-powered predictive models can look at huge amounts of data and make predictions about future demand. This can help logistics companies better manage their warehouses and move their goods around. AI systems can look at traffic patterns in real time and find the best delivery routes. This can help logistics companies save money on petrol and get things to customers faster, among other things. Automated warehousing and robotics in warehouses can save money and make things run more smoothly. Businesses can also use different chat bots and virtual assistants to make their customers' experiences better. Using AI and data is good for the transportation industry. Using traffic data and AI systems can help with managing traffic. "Project Green Light" is one such example (AI Magazine, 2025) . It is an analytical system that gathers traffic data, uses AI to analyse it, and suggests ways to improve traffic signals in Abu Dhabi. The use of AI in these fields has led to economic growth by creating new businesses in the area.

In October 2019,

“Abu Dhabi..... announced the establishment of the Mohamed bin Zayed University of Artificial Intelligence, MBZUAI, the first graduate level, research-based AI university in the world (Emirates News Agency-WAM, 2019).”

The construction of Mega City NEOM near the mouth of the Red Sea is already underway, and it will be totally run and managed by AI. Additionally, AI is intended to aid in the automation of the transportation

industry. Today, many cars feature a drive function that AI provides. In the sphere of health, AI is assisting in providing medical results with future projections. For example, Egypt's ICT ministry and Alexandria University have created artificial intelligence to detect early indicators of diabetic retinopathy. AI advancements will alter the way machines have previously operated. AI will be very helpful in many different fields and sectors. One may conclude that the application of AI in all domains contributes to future sustainability since it helps the knowledge industry learn about the type and level of soil, the treatments needed to maintain healthy soil, and other agricultural needs. AI will also boost the economy, specifically the GDP of West Asian nations. Even though this is just the beginning, the graph below (3) shows how the GDP growth of West Asian republics is astounding across a number of sectors.

Graph 3: Contribution of AI to West Asian GDP by 2030 (by Industry).

All figures are approximates.

Source: Data collected from, Price Waterhouse Coopers (PWC), “Which regions will gain the most from AI?”, Accessed 10th December 2023. See, <https://www.pwc.com/m1/en/publications/potential-impact-artificial-intelligence-middle-east.html>

The region has aspirations to incorporate AI into its economy. For example, economically prosperous countries such as Jordan, Kuwait, and Turkey are using AI's capabilities by implementing a variety of tactics that promote AI-based technology.

For instance,

“The oldest Islamic bank in Kuwait will be implementing artificial intelligence (AI) in its operations, becoming the first bank in the State to do so (Tan, 2018).”

AI is also revolutionising another crucial profession in the region, i.e. finance. According to Finastra’s Financial Services State of the Nation 2024 report, AI integration in the sector is not just accelerating innovation — it could contribute a staggering 13.6 per cent to regional GDP by 2030 (Methri, 2025). AI is projected to increase the efficiency of banking staff, thus improving banking and financial services. AI can be useful in a variety of processes, including data entry and processing, improved fraud detection capabilities, and even predictive analysis for financial forecasts.

Another important area that expects significant transformation and capacity upgrades is defence and security. In the West Asian region, Turkey is a large state that has previously invested in military production and has created a rather strong drone and other armament production capability. Now, AI is being used in the defence sector, and it is already enhancing the efficiency of such platforms. The new generation of Turkish drones, the TB2T-AI, is equipped with advanced AI capabilities (Baykar, 2025). It will have AI-powered smart flight capabilities. It can perform takeoff and landing on its own by visually recognizing runways. This AI technology can also be used to identify and assess targets, improving the lethality of drones as killing machines in a number of military scenarios. These countries have a vast amount of data that their governments employ to build artificial intelligence in the face of escalating instability in West Asia, which also has a dynamic and unstable social fabric. An excellent illustration of this is the 2011 upheaval, in which people rebelled against governments and demanded their rights in the political, social, and economic spheres. Billions of dollars are being invested in these countries, resulting in new laws and a change in the rentier structures. This can be demonstrated using an illustration.

“....., in August 2019, it (Saudi Arabia) issued a royal decree to establish a National Authority for Data and AI, and hosted in October 2020 a virtual Global AI Summit (originally scheduled for May 2020 in Riyadh but delayed due to the corona virus pandemic), touted to be the largest AI meetup of its kind, under

the patronage of Crown Prince Mohammad bin Salman (Azar & Haddad, 2021, p. 5)”.

Similarly, the Kingdom of Bahrain has also introduced the AI Society,

“..... that was created in 2018 with activities ranging from awareness regarding AI to lectures discussing AI techniques. The Artificial Intelligence Society is described as “an independent and voluntary technological society formed in 2018 with the aim of promoting and disseminating Artificial Intelligence technology across the Kingdom (Al-Ammal & Aljawder, 2021, p. 55).”

Today, data and its processing, which are required in AI, have become a new resource, with many countries betting on it. Stable economies in the region benefit Western countries that control the technical landscape. Western countries and certain Asian economies appear to be introducing AI technology; Hanson Robotics, located in Hong Kong, for example, built the robot Sophia. Consequently, competition is expected to arise across West Asia for the use of AI in various businesses.

Impact of AI on West Asia:

AI opens up new prospects in almost every industry of the business. AI enables individuals to fulfil their wants through rapid technological advancements. Some sources claim that AI will boost economic growth. While economic growth occurs, there is a cost in terms of the benefits and drawbacks of AI. AI's social ramifications include the ability to provide opportunities to all individuals through the use of AI-based apps. As a result, a big number of people can access various forms of knowledge sharing and know-how. The latest AI tool, Chat-Bot, attempts to answer the majority of questions and queries in the early stages, hence increasing reliability and confidence between the consumer and the producer or seller.

Sen mentions in his blog,

“.....the impact of AI on society is both exciting and challenging. AI has the potential to transform the way we work,

West Asia and the Emerging Geopolitics of Artificial Intelligence (AI) - Ghoble

communicate, and interact with technology, but it also raises concerns about the displacement of jobs, bias and discrimination, and the potential for misuse or abuse (Sen, 2023)."

As a result, the social implications of AI are apparent and cause concern. Social aspects such as job generation in the field of AI are profitable. However, it may result in unemployment among the unskilled work force in the coming years. As AI advances, more individuals are losing their employment in the labour market. This shift is already evident in larger industries, such as machine assembly lines, where much of the work is done by automated machines.

"..... AI-driven automation in factories will undercut the one economic advantage developing countries historically possessed: cheap labour (Lee, 2018, p. 30)."

As a result, machines equipped with AI will be able to compete in the employment market. As a result, persons with limited or no AI skills will risk unemployment. As a result, there will be a significant gap between people with AI skills and those with traditional expertise, causing a severe issue with unemployment.

"Despite the many benefits of AI, there are also concerns about its impact on society. One of the biggest concerns is the potential for AI systems to perpetuate bias and discrimination. This is because AI systems are only as unbiased as the data they are trained on. If the data is biased, then the AI system will be biased as well. For example, facial recognition systems have been shown to be less accurate for people with darker skin tones, highlighting the need for better diversity and inclusivity in AI development (Sen, 2023)."

AI would aid in linking society to numerous apps that bring people together, hence offering new employment prospects. As a result, artificial intelligence has both positive and negative social consequences. Economically, an AI-powered ecosystem will convert every segment. It is increasingly becoming the 'new normal' in how the world thinks and behaves. AI-powered solutions are projected to conquer significant markets and create billions in income. With the automation of industry processes and the refinement and polishing of products, quality

improves; thus, the economic benefits of AI are enormous. People in West Asia have accepted and are gradually aligning themselves with AI-powered applications. Thus, it is believed that the region, which was previously resistant to embrace any type of foreign instrument and considered it a cultural invasion, is now accepting the idea and concept of the AI revolution, which is changing and making their lives easier. The Gulf countries of West Asia are primarily focused on AI adaption as they create a non-oil economy. Proven to be motivating, it is clear that AI's impact is far bigger than can be articulated. In many ways, AI is like a resource that can be used and developed. Similar to the discovery of oil and its subsequent availability in West Asia, which was a game changer for the world economy, AI's role will be a game changer in the future decade, benefiting people in the social, political, and economic spheres.

The AI boom will have a significant impact in West Asia, since governments and civil society would be left behind if they refuse to accept change. The continuous conflicts in West Asia have pushed certain countries to the brink of civil war, classifying them as failed states. Yemen is one such example, with the historical struggle between North and South Yemen escalating into a sectarian and geopolitical-geo-economic warfare. The expansion of AI technology in the defence sector may exacerbate the harm to such countries as diverse non-state actors get emboldened by the ability to develop such weapons in the future. Such countries cannot benefit from technology advancement or AI-driven growth. Higher oil income and sovereign wealth funds in West Asia will result in increased investment in other areas, including AI's development. Thus, oil earnings continued to support the economies of several West Asian countries. This raises an important point: even futuristic technologies such as AI and its rate of development in these countries are still influenced by the price of a barrel of oil.

V. Way Forward:

It's also important to remember that AI is common in highly urbanised areas. Automated cameras are helpful for data transmission to the back office, traffic control, and monitoring traffic regulations. However, as time passes, AI's use will gain endurance, become addictive, and revolutionise lifestyle. AI in social media can also help anticipate the future of such elements through content analysis. As AI expertise advances, less developed countries will reap the benefits of AI-based

West Asia and the Emerging Geopolitics of Artificial Intelligence (AI) - Ghoble

technologies. This will be beneficial in the field of education, where the emphasis will be analytical and skill-based.

AI's growth and sustainability are in their early phases. The investment made by regional countries will determine AI development and augmentation. West Asian countries must also develop the logic for picking investment areas in order to achieve their AI goals. Technological innovation can help fulfil the goals of the twenty-first century, and artificial intelligence is one way to reach geopolitical and economic objectives in West Asia. Nonetheless, West Asian countries have a variety of financial systems that are plagued by both natural and man-made calamities such as sectarianism and wars, making it unlikely that the countries will make significant progress. Other health-related unfavourable variables are also on the rise, particularly among youngsters in West Asian nations.

Helen and Sahar mention that,

“As a contributor to increasing childhood obesity in the UAE and Kingdom of Saudi Arabia, the rapid rise of mobile entertainment has also become a major public concern that involves AI in the region (Abadzi & ElAsad, 2021, p. 262).”

It might be argued that economically advanced countries such as the UAE and Saudi Arabia have leverage and can benefit from oil resources that can be invested in the development of an AI-powered society. The corporate sector also collaborates extensively with West Asian countries and governments to research and implement AI in a variety of fields, including education.

For instance,

“An AI system that has already managed to get its digital education platform into dozens of schools in Abu Dhabi and Al Ain is Alef Education. Although it was established only four years ago, Alef Education has worked closely with the UAE government bringing the platform to over 25,000 students in 57 public schools (Abadzi & ElAsad, 2021, p. 262).”

As the globe experiences a geopolitical and technological transition due to AI development, the goal is to revolutionise how states behave and

operate. Thus, states should be able to enact legislation or control how AI is applied.

In the words of Badran Ahmed,

“The absence of a designated law for AI (for instance,) in Qatar further complicates the debate about AI regulation. Hence, the first step in regulating AI in Qatar should be the issuance of an AI-specific law that lays the ground rules for such a fast-growing sector and govern the behaviour of all involved actors (Badran, 2021, p. 84).”

Another significant aspect for AI's progress is public trust and confidence in governments. In a setting where West Asia is known as a critical geography that has experienced a catastrophe, people's trust is paramount. Apparently, the social and cultural origin of AI in West Asia is being driven by public and private businesses exchanging technical know-how based on trust and responsibility. However, it has made minimal progress in West Asia.

The World Economic Forum (WEF) report mentions,

“The Fourth Industrial Revolution has presented the Middle East and North Africa with unprecedented challenges that need to be solved through community innovation, collaboration and technology (World Economic Forum, 2019).”

Individual privacy and data connected with him/her are critical challenges in AI. As a result, West Asian governments and private organisations must exercise caution when handling data. Today, markets are heavily distorted, and far-flung industrial processing units are used due to the cheap labour available in those places; however, this will change with AI-operated technical procedures that reduce distance and bring industries closer to their markets. This reduces the time required to manufacture and export products to clients, but it also raises unemployment rates. Although AI is still in its early stages of research, it is a significant step forward for West Asian countries to incorporate technology into their daily lives. As AI governance takes shape in West Asia, its development, use, implementation, and governmental oversight will define its success in the next decades.

References:

- Abadzi, Helen and Sahar ElAsad, "The Art and Science of User Exploitation: AI in the UAE and Beyond", p. 262. In, Azar, Elie and Anthony N. Haddad (Eds.) (2021), "Artificial Intelligence in the Gulf: Challenges and Opportunities", Palgrave Macmillan Publications.
- Abadzi, Helen and Sahar ElAsad, "The Art and Science of User Exploitation: AI in the UAE and Beyond", p. 260. In, Azar, Elie and Anthony N. Haddad (Eds.) (2021), "Artificial Intelligence in the Gulf: Challenges and Opportunities", Palgrave Macmillan Publications.
- Abadzi, Helen and Sahar ElAsad, "The Art and Science of User Exploitation: AI in the UAE and Beyond", p. 262. In, Azar, Elie and Anthony N. Haddad (Eds.) (2021), "Artificial Intelligence in the Gulf: Challenges and Opportunities", Palgrave Macmillan Publications.
- ADNOC (March 5, 2024), "\$500 Million in Value Generated by ADNOC through Deployment of AI Solutions in 2023". Accessed 23rd October 2025. See, [https://www.adnoc.ae/en/news-and-media/press-releases/2023/\\$500-million-in-value-generated-by-adnoc-through-deployment-of-ai-solutions-in-2023](https://www.adnoc.ae/en/news-and-media/press-releases/2023/$500-million-in-value-generated-by-adnoc-through-deployment-of-ai-solutions-in-2023)
- Al-Ammal, Hesham and Maan Aljawder, "Strategy for Artificial Intelligence in Bahrain: Challenges and Opportunities", p. 55. In, Azar, Elie and Anthony N. Haddad (Eds.) (2021), "Artificial Intelligence in the Gulf: Challenges and Opportunities", Palgrave Macmillan Publications.
- Badran, Ahmed, "Thoughts and Reflections on the Case of Qatar: Should Artificial Intelligence Be Regulated?", p. 84. In, Azar, Elie and Anthony N. Haddad (Eds.) (2021), "Artificial Intelligence in the Gulf: Challenges and Opportunities", Palgrave Macmillan Publications.
- Dubai Future Foundation, "One Million Arab Coders". Accessed 23rd October 2025. See, <https://www.dubaifuture.ae/arab-coders/about-us>
- Elie Azar and Anthony N. Haddad, "An Introduction to AI in the GCC", p. 5. In, Azar, Elie and Anthony N. Haddad (Eds.) (2021), "Artificial Intelligence in the Gulf: Challenges and Opportunities", Palgrave Macmillan Publications.
- Emirates News Agency-WAM (October 16, 2019), "Abu Dhabi announces establishment of the Mohamed bin Zayed University of Artificial Intelligence". Accessed 04th January 2024. See, <https://wam.ae/en/details/1395302795116>
- FDM (22.03.2024), "Top 10 applications of AI in the energy sector", Consultancy Services Team. Accessed 26th May 2024. See, <https://www.fdmgroup.com/news-insights/ai-in-energy-sector/#:~:text=AI%20can%20also%20assist%20in,shift%20toward%20renewable%20energy%20sources>

- Ghoble, Vrushal T. (2023), *West Asia and the World: Geopolitical Shifts, Multipolarity and Energy Development*, New Delhi: Primus Books, p. 30.
- In, Price Waterhouse Coopers (PWC), “US\$320 billion by 2030? The potential impact of AI in the Middle East”, p. 6. Accessed 10th December 2023. See, <https://www.pwc.com/m1/en/publications/documents/economic-potential-ai-middle-east.pdf>
- Kennedy, Alan (September 13, 2023) “Ranked: Artificial Intelligence Startups, by Country”. Accessed 09th December 2023. See, <https://www.visualcapitalist.com/sp/global-ai-investment/#:~:text=The%20United%20States%20and%20China,invested%20in%204%2C643%20companies%20cumulatively>
- King Faisal Specialist Hospital & Research Centre (KFSH&RC) (26/6/2024), “King Faisal Specialist Hospital & Research Centre (KFSH&RC) Leads the Global Healthcare Revolution with AI and Robotics”. Accessed 23rd October 2025. See, <https://www.kfshrc.edu.sa/en/news/2024/06/kfshrc-leads-the-global-healthcare-revolution-with-ai-and-robotics>
- Lee, Kai-Fu (2018), “AI Superpowers: China, Silicon Valley, and the New World Order”, Houghton Mifflin Hartcourt: Boston, New York, p. 30.
- Methri, Gloria (April 11, 2025), “AI in Middle East banking could add 13.6% to GDP by 2030, reveals report”, IBS intelligence. Accessed 23rd October 2025. See, <https://ibsintelligence.com/ibsi-news/ai-in-middle-east-banking-could-add-13-6-to-gdp-by-2030/>
- Mubarki, Akhter Hemayoun (18 Jan 2024), “Revolutionizing Healthcare in the Middle East with the Power of AI”, innovaccer.com. Accessed 26th May 2024. See, <https://innovaccer.com/middle-east/resources/blogs/revolutionizing-healthcare-in-middle-east-with-the-power-of-ai>
- Pant, Girijesh and Vrushal T. Ghoble, "Political Economy of Geoeconomic Shift in Saudi Arabia", *Journal of West Asian Studies*, Vol. 35, Issue: January – December 2023, p. 04. Available at, <https://api.amu.ac.in/storage/file/74/journals/1714717605.pdf>
- Price Waterhouse Coopers (PWC), “Which regions will gain the most from AI?”, Accessed 10th December 2023. See, <https://www.pwc.com/m1/en/publications/potential-impact-artificial-intelligence-middle-east.html>
- Price Waterhouse Coopers (PWC), “Which regions will gain the most from AI?”, Accessed 10th December 2023. See, <https://www.pwc.com/m1/en/publications/potential-impact-artificial-intelligence-middle-east.html>

West Asia and the Emerging Geopolitics of Artificial Intelligence (AI) - Ghoble

See, “Powered by Artificial Intelligence And A Turbo Engine, BAYRAKTAR TB2T-AI UCAV Takes To The Skies”, (Feb. 22, 2025). Accessed 23rd October 2025. See, <https://baykartech.com/en/press/powered-by-artificial-intelligence-and-a-turbo-engine-bayraktar-tb2t-ai-ucav-takes-to-the-skies/>

See, <https://aimagazine.com/articles/project-green-light-google-using-ai-for-sustainability>

Sen, Amarjit (March 28, 2023), “The Impact of Artificial Intelligence on Society: Opportunities, Challenges, and Ethical Considerations”, LinkedIn.com. Accessed 10th December 2023. See, <https://www.linkedin.com/pulse/impact-artificial-intelligence-society-opportunities-challenges-sen#:~:text=One%20of%20the%20most%20profound,about%20the%20displacement%20of%20jobs.>

Sen, Amarjit (March 28, 2023), “The Impact of Artificial Intelligence on Society: Opportunities, Challenges, and Ethical Considerations”, LinkedIn.com. Accessed 10th December 2023. See, <https://www.linkedin.com/pulse/impact-artificial-intelligence-society-opportunities-challenges-sen#:~:text=One%20of%20the%20most%20profound,about%20the%20displacement%20of%20jobs.>

Tan, Vineeta (September 3, 2018), “Islamic bank becomes the first in Kuwait to integrate AI”. Accessed 04th January 2024. See, <https://ifnfintech.com/islamic-bank-becomes-the-first-in-kuwait-to-integrate-ai/>

World Economic Forum (WEF) “100 Arab startups shaping the Fourth Industrial Revolution”. Accessed 09th December 2023. See, https://www.weforum.org/impact/100-top-arab-startups/?gad_source=1&gclid=CjwKCAiAvdCrBhBREiwAX6-6UsmxRE8JdQLAwe-wnfQnEIsfWm7BAai_AuUGzsCD1ZSruI5UFsUC9hoC_twQAvD_BwE

Xiao, Wei (August 31, 2023), “Meet Five Generative AI Innovators in Africa and the Middle East”. Accessed 09th December 2023. See, <https://blogs.nvidia.com/blog/generative-ai-startups-africa-middle-east/>

Xiao, Wei (August 31, 2023), “Meet Five Generative AI Innovators in Africa and the Middle East”. Accessed 09th December 2023. See, <https://blogs.nvidia.com/blog/generative-ai-startups-africa-middle-east/>

Zartek, “Best AI Startups in the Middle East”, Blogs. Accessed 09th December 2023. See, <https://www.zartek.qa/best-ai-startups-in-the-middle-east/>